

FATIGUE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH AND FLAW GROWTH OF GRAPHITE/
EPOXY COMPOSITES UNDER SIMULATED AEROSPACE ENVIRONMENT

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This paper describes an experimental system designed to investigate the static tensile strengths of H.S. graphite/epoxy composites with various defects before and after exposure to a combined moisture-saturation plus thermal cycling in the presence of fatigue stress cycling. The moisture, thermal cycling and stress cycling were designed to simulate aerospace conditions. The equipment was designed to handle virtually any stacking arrangements and several defect types. Stress cycling is of the variable amplitude type in a fully reversed mode.

Introduction

Advanced composite aerospace components are subject to degradation in mechanical properties derived from two mechanisms: hostile environments and the growth of fabrication and service induced flaws. The purpose of the specimens and equipment described in this paper was to simulate such conditions in the laboratory, and to provide a means of accelerated testing of composites to establish that degradation.

The reduction of the stresses induced in a typical prototype aerospace component to a timewise distribution of load cycles, the appropriate staging of temperatures and humidity saturation levels appropriate to be studied are the subject of a companion paper (1)* presented at this conference and will not be elaborated upon here. The saturation level most

appropriate for the current study was established to be 1.293% weight gain. The simulative stress and temperature distribution scheme is shown in Figures 1 and 2 for single and multiple lifetime testing. The defects are described in the next section.

This paper presents a discussion of the equipment developed to meet the requirements set forth above and some preliminary results obtained to date.

The Defects

As described in reference 1, the types of defects most likely to occur, propagate and degrade composites were established through a combination of industry survey, analysis and review. Flaws likely to decrease both tension and compressive strengths, as well as to degrade bolted joint performance, were investigated. In this paper only the tension flaws will be discussed. Subsequent publications will deal with other types of flaws

The four types of flaws dealt with are described in Figure 3 and consist of 1) a hole in a composite panel, 2) an embedded sheet of foreign matter (Teflon strip), 3) a ply dropped from the composite and 4) surface scratches. The size of the critical flaw is unknown initially, and hence this study includes a means of determining this unknown. Initially flaw sizes are selected using a combination of experience and analysis. This phase is to be followed by a flaw growth study with successive screening to eliminate non-critical flaw sizes. Subsequently the study employs additional screening to establish the most critical flaw type and then, to successively investigate the behavior of that type flaw for a variety of environmental and service conditions.

Specimens

Each of the four flaw types was considered in the establishment of the specimen size and configuration. The material was selected to be AS3501-5A graphite/epoxy. Two

*Numbers in parenthesis refer to the references at the end of this paper.

FIGURE 1. SEGMENTATION OF FULLY REVERSED ($R=-1$) LOAD CYCLES TO SIMULATE ONE LIFETIME.

orientations were investigated: 1) sixteen ply $[0/+45/90/90/+45/0]_s$ layup and 2) sixteen $[0^2_2/+45]_{2s}$ layup. The specimen gage section was sized to be two inches long x 1.5 inches wide; load requirements thereby demanded a tab length of 2.5 inches on each end of the sample, thus producing an overall specimen length of seven inches (see Figure 4). Specimens, without flaws, were also prepared to serve as controls and to assist in the final data analysis.

FIGURE 2. SEGMENT SEQUENCE FOR MULTILIFE COUPON TESTING.

FIGURE 3. FLAW TYPES OF INTEREST

FIGURE 4. STATIC AND DEFECT COUPONS;
TENSILE RESIDUAL TYPE

Preconditioning

The moisture absorption by the graphite/epoxy composites was established to be 1.293% by weight. To bring the samples to this moisture level and to distribute it uniformly throughout the composite, a schedule of moisturization was established at 98% RH and 165°F. Figure 5 presents data on the moisture absorption as a function of time.

FIGURE 5. MOISTURE ABSORPTION OF 16-PLY AS3501-5A 16-PLIES COUPONS.

Approximately 21 days is required to bring samples to this established level.

A chamber consisting of distilled water reservoir, wall heaters uniformly distributed about the chamber wall, racks and platform was constructed to handle daily in-and-out logistics which insured that an orderly and routine succession of specimens be made available for testing. Frequent checks on the chamber indicated that the temperature is maintained within $\pm 3^{\circ}\text{F}$ and the humidity (wet bulb/dry bulb in flowing air) is maintained within $\pm 2, -3\%$ RH.

In practice, samples are initially dried to constant weight for 72 hours in an oven at 180°F , then preconditioned

to 1.29% \pm 0.05% moisture weight gain followed by static or fatigue testing as described later. Traveller coupons, accompanying each series of 3 to 10 replicated specimens are weighed continuously to establish the moisture loss and gain as a function of time.

Stress Cycling

Stress cycling is accomplished through the use of a servohydraulic closed-loop system. Tension and compression forces are developed by a hydraulic actuator in response to command signals from the servo controller. The feedback signal is derived from a load cell attached to the opposite end of the load frame from the actuator and in the centerline of the actuator.

Each specimen in the five-specimen chain is held by two stainless steel grips. The grip consists of two one-inch thick backup plates and two contact plates. The contact plates are faced with flame-sprayed molybdenum to form a contact surface against the specimen tabs. As shown in Figure 6, the backup plates, contact plates and specimen are symmetric about the center plane of the specimen and the center line of the actuator to load cell is contained in the specimen center plane. Each grip is designed to hold the aft end of one specimen and the forward end of the next specimen; the specimens abut each other at the center of the grip. The grips are held tightly against the specimen through the use of eight 7/16-inch stainless steel bolts tightened to an eighty foot-pound level, which was experimentally determined to be satisfactory for transmitting loads up to ten kips without slippage.

The stress-cycling contains both tensile and compressive elements. To prevent the possibility of buckling during the compression part of the loading cycle it was necessary to stabilize both the entire chain and each individual specimens. It was also necessary that this stabilization provide low resistance (through friction or restraint) to the motion of the specimens or grips. Such resistance would have provided alternate load paths, and spurious undesirable moments.

The overall chain stabilization was accomplished through two parallel Thomson rods located above and below the sample

FIGURE 6. OVERALL FATIGUE LOAD TRAIN INSIDE ENVIRONMENTAL CHAMBER.

and whose centerlines lay in the central plane of the specimens. Each Thomson rod passes through each grip through two ears attached to the inner part of the two part backup assembly plate. The ears are welded to the plate and were bored in a jig bore to receive stainless-steel ball bushings which form the contact with the Thomson rods. The two Thomson rods are in turn supported and stabilized against lateral motion by means of four stabilizer plates seated on the inside of the environmental chamber, and each of which can be adjusted through a set of six set screws. The setscrews are directly positioned against two L-plates which are located in the lower portion of the environmental chamber against the long sides and bottom of the chamber. The setscrews provide the

means of alligning the Thomson rods parallel to the actuator-specimen-load cell center line and to space them equally on both sides of this center line.

In practice the Thomson rods can be moved longitudinally during the stroking of the chain and hence provide little opportunity for the development of alternate load paths.

Finally the individual samples require stabilization against compressive loads, since they may be prone to buckling because of their length, low modulus and because of the degradation of their stiffness due to temperature, absorbed moisture, and flaw growth. From several alternative candidate stabilization schemes, an edge support system was finally selected. (see Figure 7). The need for not interfering with flaw growth became the dominant criterion in the ultimate selection of this method.

Four contacting teflon pads, each one inch long, 3/16-inch wide and approximately twenty mils thick, are located on the faces of the specimen along and centered on the edges of the gage section of the specimen. Two plates normal to the specimen are then clamped over these teflon pads and are affixed to the Thomson rods over ball bushings. These stabilization plates are free to move longitudinally, parallel to the specimens during stroking of the chain.

Humidification And Thermal Input

The samples, humidified to the desired levels in the preconditioning chamber, required humidification in the fatigue chamber (during thermal input) to retain those moisture saturation levels. Steam is the mechanism, by which this moisture level is maintained. At the start of a thermal input cycle, steam is introduced into the chamber through the computer activated steam valve. It is distributed throughout the chamber through a multi-ported copper tubing which is coiled throughout the bottom of the environmental chamber. (see Figure 8).

The environmental chamber is not designed to be a pressure containment chamber and therefore, the practical limiting temperature, above which the steam heating provides no further temperature rise in the system is approximately 212°F.

FIGURE 7. EDGE STABILIZATION FOR COMPOSITE FATIGUE SPECIMEN.

The spectrum shown in Figures 1 and 2 requires that the composite samples be heated to 235°F and 270°F during the respective cycles. Therefore an additional heating source was required above 212°F. A bank of immersion heaters on both sides of the fatigue chain provided this heat. In practice, the heaters are turned on simultaneously with the introduction of steam. The steam shuts off when the thermocouple indicates that temperature has reached 212°F. Upon reaching the desired temperature of 235°F or 270°F, the temperature is then maintained through a system of on-off controls. The controller

FIGURE 8.. ENVIRONMENTAL CHAMBER, WITHOUT
LOAD TRAIN, SHOWING STEAM COILS.

continues to maintain temperature until the conclusion of the fatigue stress cycling at which time the computer sends a command signal to the heaters and steam valves to open and close circuits as appropriate.

Stress cycling is temporarily halted during temperature and humidification changeover periods. Stress cycling begins immediately upon notification by the feedback thermocouples to the computer, that temperature has been attained, whereupon a command signal to the actuator is issued to begin operation.

Simulation System Electronic Controls

To accomplish the stress cycling spectrum previously described then becomes a task of control of the fatigue equipment. The prototype aerospace environment and the cyclic stresses are encountered randomly. The simulating spectrum is far simpler, in that groups of identical stresses and temperatures are imposed. None the less, the reduced complexity of the test spectrum still indicates a need for "smart" control. This control can be applied to conventional servo-hydraulic equipment for spectral loading, and real time control

FIGURE 9. SCHEMATIC OF THE ELECTRONIC CIRCUITRY FOR STRESS-CYCLING EQUIPMENT.

of heaters and refrigerants for environmental conditions.

Figure 9 is a schematic of the overall flow diagram for load and environmental control. In this particular application a minicomputer is used as the load controlling function generator, but also serves as a programmable temperature controller as well. The minicomputer was selected because of its "built-in" ability to digitally generate a sine-wave function which is used as the input to the servohydraulic controller. If desired or necessary for additional levels of simulation complexity, a random, or other function generated by the computer, can be stored on a disk or tape and this can be used as the input function.

Sinusoidal loading is programmed into the computer from the teletype using simple statements which include frequency, magnitude, number of cycles applied and offset. The computer executes statements in numerical succession and stops when no more statements are found. Branch and loop statements are included, as required, in the program for simplification of repetitive grouping of the stress cycles.

The digital command output from the computer is converted to an analog signal which is the load command input for the servocontroller. The servocontroller constantly readjusts the position of the actuator to match the load cell feedback signal to the analog command input. The actuator position is adjusted by hydraulic pressure controlled by the servovalve. If the load cell feedback signal and the analog command signal are not within some predetermined small range, the servocontroller interprets this as a loss of closed loop load control and an error signal is sent to both the hydraulic controls and the computer. Hydraulic controls then turn off the hydraulic pressure and the computer records the time of the event and stops producing command signals.

Concurrently, with the load controlling task described above, the computer performs all closed loop temperature controlling tasks. Statements may be included in the initial program which control the testing temperature. A temperature controlling statement may have no effect on the loading spectrum or it may halt the load command signal until the test temperature is achieved. The temperature of the testing

chamber is sensed through an RTD or thermocouple and is made intelligible to the computer through an analog to digital converter. Temperature is then controlled through three relay output channels, one for steam heating to 212°F, one for electric heating above 212°F, and one for cooldown from all temperatures.

Error detection in the closed loop temperature control circuit is provided by the computer itself. If the test temperature is not achieved in ten minutes, then the test is aborted and all heaters, actuators and valves are shut off.

An additional advantage of minicomputer control is provided by the systems ability to track the progress of the simulation test and record any significant events such as specimen failure, loss of temperature control or stop commands from an auxillary sensing device such as an acoustic emission monitor. The location in the command program at which the test is stopped, is recorded and printed out by the system teletype.

The particular location in the command program may be obtained at any time throughout the test by addressing the computer through the system teletype.

Nondestructive Inspection For Flaw Growth

Ultrasonic scanning was selected as the most appropriate method for nondestructively inspecting the specimens to detect flaw growth. This procedure is not performed during stress-cycling, but requires periodically stopping the test unit, removing the specimens, ultrasonically scanning them and replacing them for additional stress-cycling. Ultrasonic scanning is performed before stress-cycling begins and after every successive half-life of stress, temperature and humidity exposure thereafter up to as many as 4 complete lifetimes.

The ultrasonic equipment shown in Figure 10 utilizes the pulse echo mode of monitoring, in which a single transducer transmits an ultrasonic pulse and receives its echo from the specimen. The received echo contains reflections from both the specimen front and back surfaces as well as any reflecting plane between them.

The reflection from the back surface of the specimen contains information about the back surface but, additionally con-

tains information about any previous reflecting plane. If a previous reflecting plane is active then the magnitude of the back reflection decreases. The magnitude or peak output, from the specimen's back face, is therefore a measure of specimen integrity. The ultrasonic transducer scans the specimen surface in the transverse directions and each successive scan is incremented in the longitudinal direction, until the entire specimen surface has been covered. Electronically coupled with the transducer scanning movements is the pen on an x-y plotter. The pen motion records movement of the transducer and superimposed on this pen movement is the peak output recorded from the specimen's back reflecting plane. Both attenuation versus position and a simple go-no-go or gated response can and are recorded to assist in the data interpretation.

FIGURE 10. ULTRASONIC FLAW GROWTH MONITORIZATION SETUP.

↑
monitoring?

Acoustic Emission Monitorization During Stress Cycling

In order to insure against the possibility of significant growth (and possibly failure) between ultrasonic inspections it was deemed necessary to provide some means of continuous nondestructive monitorization. Acoustic emission appeared to offer the most practical means of accomplishing this continuous inspection.

Much of the flaw growth is of a nature that allows its detection by acoustic monitorization. The fatigue equipment has been designed with provisions for acoustic transducers to be placed in contact with the specimen surface during load cycling. Acoustic transducers are placed on each specimen in the chain and monitored either individually or in summation. (See Figure 11).

Information from the acoustic transducer is truncated to remove background noise; any noise level exceeding the truncation value is called a "count". The monitor transmits the count rate to both a chart recorder and an alarm circuit. The alarm circuit is passive for all count rates below a preset critical rate. However, once the critical rate has been reached, a signal from the alarm circuit is transmitted to the hydraulic control panel and the fatigue test unit is halted to permit an unscheduled ultrasonic inspection of the sample.

Summary Of Results

The results obtained from the tests performed to date are as-yet too few to make any firm conclusions. Some preliminary evidence shows that the two most serious flaw types are the hole and the surface scratch, with little or no strength reduction from the dropped ply or the embedded foreign film.

As far as the reliability of the equipment is concerned some of the checkout results indicate

- o For the tensile portion of the stress cycle in graphite samples of orientation No. 2 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$ the chain of 5 samples stressed uniformly within $\pm 8\%$ of the intended load in the worst case with an additional $\pm 5\%$ bending stress. The principal source of the $\pm 8\%$ error in the specimens is a $\pm 5\%$ thickness variation in the samples.

- o For compression portion of the stress cycle the chain of 5 samples are stressed uniformly within $\pm 6\%$ of the intended load with an additional $\pm 5\%$ bending stress.
- o Tensile static tests in the fixture indicate that a dynamic compressive overshoot of from 25 to 50% of peak stress at failure is induced in the other samples in the chain.
- o Temperature control from RT to 270°F was within $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{F}$ at the plateau and from RT to -65°F was within $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{F}$ in the worst case. The longest stabilization time required was at -65°F requiring 10 minutes.

FIGURE 11. ACOUSTIC EMISSION TRANSDUCER AS MOUNTED ON SPECIMEN AND SUPPORTED BY COMPRESSION STABILIZATION PLATE

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References

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